

Influence of Climate Change on the Health of Children in Foster Care: Implication for Sustainable Social Adjustment of Children

Agahiu E. G. Kembe E.M. & Ivande P.D

Abstract

The greatest vulnerability risk to climate change is directed towards children. In a situation where children are not under the control of their biological parents but in foster care, there is even more concern on the possibility of their adaptation to climate change. Children in foster care may already have psychological and emotionally instability and exposure to poor climatic factors may be a great risk to their growth and development or survival in entirety. There are several ways in which climate change influence the health of children; these include: increased air pollution, more weather-related disasters, more frequent and intense heat waves, decreased water quality and quantity, food shortage and greater exposure to toxicants. For children in foster care, it is concluded that climate change may result to risk of mental disorders, malnutrition, infectious diseases, allergic diseases and respiratory diseases. It is therefore recommended that, control and prevention measures such as reducing carbon pollution emissions and adaptation measures such as early warning systems and post-disaster counseling should be employed.

Keywords: Children, Foster Care, Climate Change, Social adjustment, Vulnerability

Introduction

Climate change has proven to be one of the biggest development challenges of the twenty-first century. Communities in every country are already experiencing the impact of extreme weather events, temperature changes and disease outbreaks. Although it is practically impossible to be immune to the effects of climate change, children on a general note are particularly vulnerable. Vulnerability entails the quality or state of being exposed to the possibility of being attacked or harmed, either physically or emotionally by a phenomenon. When children are in foster care, the vulnerability ratio is higher to environmental factors (Schiermeier, 2011).

Greenhouse gas emissions have committed the world to a range of adverse and potentially catastrophic effects that will impact children. Current and future generations of children face declining water security, rising pressures on food production

and increasing disasters and disease risks, with long-term consequences on their development. This is particularly alarming because children in Africa already experience a range of challenges, from poor access to water and sanitation to malnutrition and disease (UNICEF, 2018). Children are especially sensitive to these changes because they are physiologically and metabolically less able than adults at adapting to heat and other climate-related exposure. Children are still-evolving, and their development puts them at higher risk of contracting diseases and succumbing to health-related complications due to lower immunity. Children are also more likely than adults to be killed or injured during disasters (UNICEF, 2018).

Studies such as Akachi, Goodman and Parker (2009) show that some of the main killers of children are highly sensitive to changes in the climate. For example,

temperature increase has been linked to increases in the burden of malnutrition, cholera, diarrheal disease and vector-borne diseases like dengue and malaria. Climate change impact are also projected to increase the number of children affected by natural hazards, from an estimated 66.5 million per year in the late 1990s to as many as 175 million per year globally in the coming decade, (Akachi, Goodman and Parker, 2009). Even moderate climate change impacts could have profound long-term consequences on foster children's overall development (McKibbin and Wilcoxon, 2004).

Climate change and environmental degradation are undermining children's rights, especially the most disadvantaged. Children are disproportionately vulnerable to the impact of climate change. The specific nature of their vulnerability is multidimensional, shaped largely by the physical, social, and emotional changes that take place over the course of childhood (IPCC, 2007).

Every child has the right to life, health, education and development and to have their interests considered by adults. Addressing the impact of climate change and reducing greenhouse gas emission is imperative for protecting the world's most vulnerable children such as those in foster care. Children from the poorest and most marginalized families are especially vulnerable to the impact of climate change, even though children have contributed the least to the causes of climate change (greenhouse gas emissions from energy, forestry and agriculture) and live in the most degraded or polluted environment (McKibbin and Wilcoxon, 2020).

Every year, household air pollution contributes to over half a million deaths of children under five from acute respiratory infections, a critical issue for UNICEF. Air pollution in urban areas, risks from chemicals, waste, polluted water, and the lack of green and clean areas for children to play are crucial issues for UNICEF (Mathieu-Nolf, 2012).

Compared with adults, children breathe more air, drink more water, and eat more

food per unit of body weight. Children often play outdoors, and are expected to live longer than adults, exposing them to newly developing or worsening environmental hazards in the future. Additionally, many diseases like smallpox have a long latency period, sometimes requiring decades to develop. Children hand to mouth behavior, and the fact that they live and play close to the ground further increases children's exposure to environmental hazards. There has been increasing interest in climate change's impact on children's health. Though warming in cold regions may have some beneficial effects on children (e.g., reducing some cold-related deaths and diseases, such as viral diarrheal and respiratory infections), the negative impact of climate change on children may far outweigh the positive effects.

Mathieu-Nolf, (2012) noted the children's potential vulnerability to climate change but the mechanisms of such vulnerability and the exact situation for disadvantaged children such as those in foster care is yet to be explored. This paper will articulate the mechanisms of children's vulnerability to climate change and discuss mitigation and adaptation strategies for preventing foster children from the harmful effect of climate change.

Climate Change, Measuring vulnerability and foster care

Climate change is a change in the pattern of weather, and related changes in oceans, land surfaces and ice sheets, occurring over time. Weather is the state of the atmosphere, its temperature, humidity, wind, rainfall over hours to weeks. It is influenced by the oceans, land surfaces and ice sheets, which together with the atmosphere form what is called the 'climate system'. Climate, in its broadest sense, is the statistical description of the state of the climate system (IPCC, 2007).

Climate change is a change in the statistical properties of the climate system that persists for several decades or longer usually at least 30 years. These statistical properties include averages, variability and extremes. Climate change may be due to natural processes, such as changes in the

sun's radiation, volcanoes or internal variability in the climate system, or due to human influences such as changes in the composition of the atmosphere or land use (Bunyavanich, 2003).

Weather can be forecast with considerable skill up to about a week in advance. Short term fluctuations in climate, such as droughts, can be predicted with limited skill from season to season. In contrast, changes in the long-term statistics of the climate system (climate change) can be predicted if caused by long-term influences that are known or predictable (McMichael and Butler, 2004).

Climate is determined by many factors that influence flow of energy through the climate system, including greenhouse gases. Energy from the sun is the ultimate driver of climate on Earth. The solar energy received by Earth depends on how much the Sun emits and the distance between Earth and the Sun. Part of this sunlight is reflected directly back to space by the atmosphere, clouds, land, ice and water surfaces. Aerosols (tiny particles in the atmosphere, some coming from human activities) can increase the reflection of sunlight (Akachiet *al.*, 2009).

The solar energy absorbed by Earth is returned to space as infrared (heat) radiation. In the process it interacts with the whole climate system atmosphere, oceans, land surfaces and ice sheets. The flow of radiation in the atmosphere are very important in determining climate. The main gases that make up the atmosphere, nitrogen and oxygen, do not interact with infrared radiation. However, certain gases present in smaller quantities absorb infrared radiation flowing upwards from Earth's surface and re-radiate it in all directions, including back and downwards. By doing this, they impede the outward flow of infrared energy from Earth to space. This is called the 'greenhouse effect', and the gases that cause it by interacting with infrared radiation are called greenhouse gases. The most important are water vapor, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane. The greenhouse effect was identified more than a century ago; Earth's surface would be about 33°C cooler without

it, so it keeps Earth habitable (IPCC, 2007).

Global climate varies naturally over time scales from decades to thousands of years and longer. These natural variations can originate in two ways: from internal fluctuations that exchange energy, water and carbon between the atmosphere, oceans, land and ice, and from external influences on the climate system, including variations in the energy received from the sun and the effects of volcanic eruptions. Human activities can also influence climate by changing concentrations of CO₂ and other greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, altering the concentrations of aerosols and altering the reflectivity of Earth's surface by changing land cover.

In climate change and disaster risk research, vulnerability has been related to resilience, exposure, sensitivity, coping capacity, adaptability and risk. The multiple use of the term may lead to confusion about who is vulnerable to climate change and may also cause a loss of clarity as to the causes and consequences of vulnerability, (IPCC, 2007).

In this paper, 'vulnerability' refers to the characteristics and circumstances of a person, community, system or asset that make it susceptible to the effects of climate change and other hazards. It is often expressed as a function of physical exposure to hazards, sensitivity to the stresses they impose and capacity to adapt to various stresses (Akachiet *al.*, 2009).

Vulnerability at either the individual or community level depends on a range of factors, such as population density, age distribution, economic development, dependence on climate-sensitive sectors, food availability, health status, prevalence of climate-sensitive diseases, local environmental and geographical conditions and quality and availability of social services, including health care. Underlying these components are economic, socio-demographic and legislative processes that collectively or independently include or exclude certain populations from accessing services and realizing their rights as citizens (Mathieu-Nolf, 2012). Children in foster care have a high propensity to vulnerability.

Foster care is a system enabling a child without parental support and protection to be placed with a person or family to be cared for, usually by local welfare services or by court order. The foster parent(s) do not have custody, nor is there an adoption, but they are expected to treat the foster child as they would their own in regard to food, housing, clothing and education. Most foster parents are paid by the local government or a state agency.

The child's parents may retain their parental rights, and the child may ultimately return home. Under permanent foster care the agency has guardianship; the child may then be available for adoption by the foster parents or others. Foster care can also provide a supervised setting for adults with mental or emotional disabilities who cannot care adequately for themselves. The concept of foster care has been extended in recent years to include care for elderly persons, on a fee basis, in the homes of people who are not family members (Back and Cameron, 2008).

Foster care is a system in which a minor has been placed into a ward, group home, or private home of a state certified caregiver, referred to as a "foster parent". The placement of the child is normally arranged through the government or a social service agency. The institution, group home or foster parent is compensated for expenses. Children in foster care are vulnerable to both direct and indirect environmental hazards resulting from climate change.

Climate Change and Air Pollution

Air Pollution

Air pollution is closely associated with climate change and is expected to worsen as climate change continues. Climate change will affect future air quality through perturbing ventilation rates, precipitation scavenging, dry deposition, chemical production and loss rates, natural emissions, and background concentrations (Back and Cameron, 2008).

Children on a general note, together with elderly, represent subpopulations particularly sensitive to the negative health effects of air pollution. The situation is worst

for those in foster care. Their exposure to outdoor particulate matter has been associated with respiratory symptoms, decreased lung function, worsening of asthma and the development of chronic bronchitis. Ozone exposure may also render a number of adverse health effects in foster care children, including shortness of breath,

Weather-Related Disasters

Climate change increases the frequency and intensity of floods, droughts, bushfires and cyclones. Exposure to natural disasters was reported to exacerbate the burden of depression, anxiety and stress. High rates of sleep disturbance, sadness, and other mental health impairments among children are associated with weather-related disasters. In addition, high stress for adults after weather-related disasters can have serious implications for children, by impeding the adults' ability as caregivers and in extreme circumstances resulting in neglect and even abuse (Back and Cameron, 2008).

Heat Waves

Heat waves, sporadic periods of elevated temperatures outside the normal range of climate variability, occur throughout the world and are projected to become more frequent and intense in the future. Children are particularly vulnerable to heat waves. Children's renal disease is an important consequence of heat waves (Woodruff and McMichael, 2004). Exposure to extreme hot weather can induce heat-related conditions including hyperthermia and heat stress in children, and the renal system can be stressed or compromised by a range of reflexive thermoregulatory, physiological, and circulatory adjustments. Respiratory diseases also increase among children during heat wave periods. With the poor condition of shelter in most foster care homes, children are bound to suffer the full consequences of excess heat (Shea, 2008).

Climate change is threatening a number of fragile ecosystems. Children's health depends on the continuous supply of various ecological services, the conditions and processes through which natural ecosystems,

and the species that make them up, sustain and fulfill human life”, and ecological services are underpinned by biodiversity which is also threatened by a number of climate change mechanisms. In addition, rising sea levels and inundation of coastal areas, exacerbated by climate change, could render major disruption of social systems (Talmage and Gobler, 2011).

Decreased Water Quality and Quantity

Climate change alters the hydrologic cycle, melting sea ice, accelerating evaporation from sea and other surface waters, increasing the frequency and intensity of precipitation in some areas, and triggering drought in other areas (IPCC, 2007). Ground and surface water supplies can run short because of drought, and rising sea levels can cause saltwater intrusion into groundwater. Storms and floods can compromise supplies of clean water (The Center for Health and the Global Environment, Harvard Medical School, 2006). As the temperatures rise, the replication of the pathogens which water carries (protozoa, bacteria and viruses) will also increase. Contaminated water is the major cause of malnutrition and diarrheal disease, which remain a leading cause of death in children under five years of age (Prüss-Ustün, Bos, Gore and Bartram, 2008).

Food Supply Shortage

Increased evaporation dehydrates soils, and flooding salinates other arable land, diminishing agricultural area and productivity (McMichael, 2001). Children require three or four times more food per unit of bodyweight than adults and comprise the majority of the global population plagued by hunger (Cohen, Tirado, Aberman, 2008). Declining food production and rising food prices will exacerbate the global rates of malnutrition and stunting, and further threatening children's health especially those in foster care.

Toxicant Exposure

As climate change continues, temperature, humidity and hydrologic cycles change, and the distribution of environmental toxicants change subsequently (Booth and Zeller, 2005). Increased precipitation and ice snow melt in some areas may enhance wet deposition of

persistent organic pollutants to aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems (Meyer and Wania, 2008). Regions of decreased precipitation might experience more volatilization of persistent organic pollutants and pesticides to the atmosphere.

Rising temperature will enhance the toxicity of contaminants and increase concentrations of tropospheric ozone regionally. Consequently, children in foster care may experience greater exposure to toxic substances. Exposure to a wide range of chemicals and environmental toxicants during childhood, especially chemical neurotoxicants, may affect the development, maturation, growth and function of organ systems of children. Children in foster care just like other children are particularly vulnerable to the neurotoxic effects of lead; low levels of exposure can reduce intelligence quotient scores, and cause learning disabilities (WHO, 2002).

Infectious Diseases

Climate change may influence the replication rates, survival and transmission of infectious disease pathogens which can happen even in foster homes. Storms and floods may result in crop contamination and drinking water contamination which leads to illness. Compared with adults, children consume a larger relative proportion of fruits and vegetables and spend a larger proportion of time outdoors, increasing climate-sensitive exposures such as pesticide residues on food and outdoor insect vectors. Their relatively naïve immune systems increase the risk of serious consequences from water- and food-borne diseases. Children in foster care with a probable lower immune system are therefore vulnerable to infectious diseases as a result of climate change.

Allergic Diseases

Childhood asthma is a widespread health problem because of its epidemic

prevalence.

Pollen counts could rise due to multiple mechanisms such as increased ambient CO₂ levels, increased temperature, or earlier spring seasons (Wayne *et al.*, 2002). Elevated CO₂ concentration often increases plant leaf biomass and carbon-to-nitrogen ratio which can affect not only pollen but also mold. Elevated ambient CO₂ levels are associated with increased fungal spore production, a potential asthma trigger. Increased temperature can also affect spatial distribution and density of plants and fungi that produce aeroallergens.

Allergic disease will also likely be worsened because of interaction between climate change impact on thunderstorms which can fractionate pollen into smaller particles; extreme precipitation events; and increasing heat-related ground-level ozone pollution (Shea, 2008). The current global increase in childhood asthma can be partly explained by increased exposure to aeroallergens driven by climate change.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Children in foster care are uniquely vulnerable to climate change, despite that some research has been done on evaluating the impact of climate change on children's health, specific works on those with special needs are urgently needed. For children in foster care, it is concluded that climate change may result to risk of mental disorders, malnutrition, infectious diseases, allergic diseases and respiratory diseases. It is therefore recommended that, control and prevention measures such as reducing carbon pollution emissions and adaptation measures such as early warning systems and post-disaster counseling should be employed. Also, children in foster care should be given additional attention by care givers in terms of feeding, cleanliness and shelter so to reduce their vulnerability to issues associated with climate change.

References.

Akachi, Y.; Goodman, D.; Parker, D (2009). *Global Climate Change and Child Health: A Review of Pathways, Impacts and*

Measures to Improve the Evidence Base. New York: UNICEF.

- Back, E.; Cameron, C (2008). *Our Climate, Our Children, Our Responsibility. The Implications of Climate Change for World's Children.* New York: UNICEF
- Bunyavanich S, Christopher P. Landrigan, Anthony J. McMichael, Paul R. Epstein (2003). The Impact of Climate Change on Child Health, *Ambulatory Pediatrics*, Volume 3, Issue 1, Pages 44-52.
- Chang, Y., Schlenstedt, G., Flockerzi, V., Beck, A (2010). Properties of the intracellular transient receptor potential (TRP) channel in yeast, Yvc1. *FEBS Lett* 584(10):2028-32.
- IPCC, 2007: *Climate Change 2007: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* [Core Writing Team, Pachauri, R.K and Reisinger, A. (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, 104 pp.
- Mathieu-Nolf, M (2012). Poisons in the air: A cause of chronic disease in children. *J. Toxicol. Clin. Toxicol.* 40, 483-491.
- McKibbin, W.J., Wilcoxon, P.J (2020). Climate policy and uncertainty: The roles of adaptation *versus* mitigation. In *Brookings Discussion Papers in International Economics*. The Brookings Institution: Washington, DC, USA.
- McMichael, A. J., Butler, C. D. (2004). *Climate Change and Human Health: Risks and Responses.* WHO/World Meteorological Organization, Geneva.
- Schiermeier, Q (2011). Climate and weather: Extreme measures. *Nature*, 477, 148-149.
- Shea, K (2008). American Academy of Pediatrics Committee on Environmental Health. *Global Climate change and Children's Health. Pediatrics*, 120, 1149-1152.
- UNICEF (2008). *Climate Change and Children: A Human Security Challenge.* Hellenic Foundation for European and Foreign Policy. New York: UNICEF Innocenti Research Centre.